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GAMEHEARTS

EU/Comparative Policy Report

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Table of Contents

1. PROJECT SUMMARY.....	5
2. INTRODUCTION.....	6
3. METHODOLOGY.....	9
4. EU LEGAL FRAMEWORK IN THE VIDEO GAME INDUSTRY.....	11
5. REGULATORY TRENDS AND DIVERGENCES IN THE EUROPEAN VIDEO GAMING INDUSTRY.....	15
5.1 Content Regulation and Age Classification.....	15
5.2 Data Protection and Privacy.....	21
5.3 Consumer Protection and Industry Incentives.....	22
5.4 Intellectual Property and Cultural Diversity.....	22
6. REGULATING THE VIDEO GAME INDUSTRY IN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES: A COMPARATIVE OVERVIEW.....	24
6.1 Austria.....	25
6.2 Finland.....	30
6.3 Netherlands.....	34
6.4 Poland.....	38
6.5 The UK.....	43
7. OUTLOOK: FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND CHALLENGES IN THE GOVERNANCE OF THE GAMING INDUSTRY.....	48
8. RECOMMENDATIONS.....	51
9. REFERENCES.....	54
10. APPENDIX A. LIST OF INTERVIEWEES.....	66

1. Project Summary

GAMEHEARTS seeks to maximise the value of the European video game industry ecosystems (hereafter, EVGIE) within a wider social context of the creative and cultural industries (hereafter, CCI). This considers the importance of the EVGIE in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion, by particularly focusing on how a stronger and closer working relationship between more the traditional and emergent cultural sectors, can work better to create more inclusive and socially responsible cultural experiences. The consortium offers policy recommendations and roadmaps setting out how the EVGIE can and should develop, and where it could act as a driver for sustained innovation and economic growth. It will utilise an evidence-based approach that focuses not just on video game development, but rather adopts a holistic ecosystem approach, utilising both established (desk research, such as policy review, systematic literature review and field research like in-depth and focus group interviews) and more innovative methodologies (action research using design thinking marathons), to consider the competitiveness and development of the EVGIE, and how video game know-how and technologies could drive innovation in the wider CCI. In so doing, GAMEHEARTS will develop 'ludic experiences', to explore possibilities of more inclusive, engaging, and empowering cultural experiences. Working across seven work packages the universities of Salford (UK), Tampere (Finland), Vienna (Austria), Breda University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands), and Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (Poland) will work in partnership with Ubisoft (France) and other major video game partners and associations (including the Video Games Europe & EGDF) to explore current and future trends in the EVGIE. The consortium includes some key cultural case study partners in order to explore the ways on which game-related technologies and practices are, and can be, used to increase access to heritage, the arts, and sport.

2. Introduction

This report aims to compare national policy approaches with EU governance principles, examining existing industry-specific and related social policies in selected European countries. It highlights the differences and similarities between national strategies and EU-wide frameworks. It begins with an overview of the current regulatory frameworks governing the video game industry in Europe, examining how these policies either hinder or promote a commercially robust and socially beneficial video game ecosystem. The analysis underlying this report includes a detailed examination of national policies in Austria, Finland, the Netherlands, Poland and the United Kingdom, and aims to identify opportunities, risks and gaps in video games regulations in these countries and the EU. To complement this analysis, we conducted interviews with key stakeholders, ranging from academic researchers to policymakers, industry leaders, and regulatory experts.

The EU27 video games market generated revenues of €25.7 billion in 2023 and is outpacing other digital media sectors (Video Games Europe, 2023) significantly. By the end of 2024, the revenue in the EU games market is projected to reach \$73.27 billion in 2024, while the global games market will generate 177.7 billion EUR (Statista, n.d.). The COVID-19 pandemic fueled the growth of the video games market, leading to a surge in European gamers. In 2023, 124.4 million people in the European Union, or 53% of the European population aged 6 to 64, played video games (Video Games Europe, 2023). According to a report “All About Video Games – European Key Facts” by Video Games Europe¹ 74% of European video game players play at least one hour per week. On average, in 2022, people in Europe said that they spend nine hours per week playing video games, 14 hours per week on social media and 24 hours per week watching TV (Video Games Europe, 2022). These numbers remained about the same in the year of 2023. The video games industry employed 114,400 people in Europe in 2023, with 24.4% of the video games industry workforce being women (Video Games Europe, 2023).

Women constitute 46.7% of gamers (Video Games Europe, 2022: 10), 76% of video game players are 18 years or older (Video Games Europe, 2022: 9), and 71% of the 6 to 10 year children are active in gaming compared to 80% of the 11 to 14 year olds (Video Games Europe, 2022: 9). However, these groups are still inadequately represented in gaming content, industry employment (particularly adult women), and regulatory frameworks, especially when

¹ Video Games Europe represents the video games industry in Europe. It comprises 19 European and international video game companies and 13 national trade associations across Europe.

viewed through the lenses of social responsibility, care, and diversity. There is a growing recognition of the ways in which women are engaging in video gaming, participating in gaming communities, and contributing to the expansion of gaming culture. Nevertheless, no country in Europe has a female workforce in this sector that exceeds 30%. The proportion of female employees in the industry is highest in Eastern European countries (EGDF & ISFE, 2019, p.5).

Despite its rapid growth, the video game industry, long subject to traditional regulations like contract law and consumer protection legislation, now faces a surge of rules targeting broader tech sectors, including GAFA (Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon) and social media platforms, which inadvertently impact gaming. This shift coincides with the emergence of gaming-specific issues, such as controversies around loot boxes, driving the need for dedicated regulatory attention to the industry's unique dynamics. For instance, in 2023, the UK's Competition and Markets Authority (CMA) blocked Microsoft's attempt to acquire Activision, a leading video game publisher, citing concerns over the future of the cloud gaming market (CMA, 2023). Similarly, enforcement of the EU's Digital Services Act (DSA) underscores the importance of data protection in the gaming sector, as the DSA governs the responsibilities of internet intermediaries, including intermediary services that host or facilitate gaming activities. While separate data protection regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), specifically address the handling of personal data across the EU, the DSA complements these by imposing obligations on online intermediary services to safeguard user rights, ensure transparency, and address harmful content. Additionally, loot boxes have sparked global debate, especially regarding their impact on children, leading to varied regulatory responses across Europe, from self-regulation in the UK (DCMS, 2022) to outright bans in Belgium.

The following discussion focuses on industry-wide and societal concerns related to the enforcement of age restrictions, the appropriateness of content for different age groups, and issues surrounding representations, as well as issues around loot boxes and data protection.

The regulation of loot boxes across the European Union showcases a mix of national approaches and EU-wide initiatives aimed at addressing concerns over their similarities to gambling and consumer protection issues. Belgium has adopted one of the strictest stances, classifying both tradable and non-tradable loot boxes as illegal gambling under its broad gambling legislation. However, enforcement remains limited, with many games still offering loot boxes. Italy, the Netherlands, and the UK have leveraged the EU Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (UCPD) (n.d.) to impose transparency obligations, such as disclosing the presence

and probabilities of loot boxes. Austria has taken a more direct approach, ruling certain loot boxes as illegal gambling, enabling civil litigation, while Finland's efforts to prosecute loot box providers were impeded by jurisdictional challenges. At the EU level, there are preliminary discussions about classifying loot boxes as an unfair commercial practice under Annex 1 of the UCPD. This potentially would harmonise regulations across member states. However, what is clear at the moment at the EU level is that loot boxes should be addressed from a consumer protection law perspective rather than as gambling. Meanwhile, the Netherlands has faced legal obstacles in regulating loot boxes under gambling laws, with courts emphasising that loot boxes should be assessed as part of the overall gaming experience rather than as separate mechanics (Xiao, 2024).

The report is divided into thematic and country-specific sections. The first section examines the overarching regulatory trends in the European video game industry, such as content regulation, age classification, and consumer protection. Following this, the report focuses on the country-specific analyses of Austria, Finland, the Netherlands, Poland, and the United Kingdom, to examine their unique national policies, regulatory approaches, and implementation strategies. This section highlights key similarities and differences among these countries, offering a comparative perspective on how regulations address issues such as consumer data protection, diversity and inclusivity, youth protection, and loot boxes. The final section synthesises the findings by exploring broader regulatory trends and divergences within the European video gaming industry, concluding with recommendations for harmonising policies and addressing emerging challenges in the rapidly evolving digital landscape.

3. Methodology

This report employs a mixed-method research approach, integrating elements of cocreation with stakeholders, desk research and in-depth interviews with resource individuals to provide a comprehensive analysis of the regulatory landscape of the European video game industry. The desk research component involves systematic policy reviews and literature reviews, including grey literature, in order to map and identify existing regulatory frameworks, trends, and gaps in national and EU-level video game regulations. These reviews serve as the foundation for understanding the broader regulatory environment and its implications for the European video game ecosystem. The report pays attention to concurrent debates around regulatory efforts and signposts challenges and expectations as these are articulated in publicly available documents.

Complementing the desk research, field research was conducted through in-depth interviews with a diverse range of stakeholders. Participants included academic researchers, policymakers, industry leaders, and regulatory experts (see Appendix). We conducted 15 interviews with resource individuals amounting to a total of 542 minutes. These interviews provided confirmation, highlights and valuable insights into current trends, risks, and opportunities in video game regulations across Austria, Finland, the Netherlands, Poland, and the United Kingdom. The qualitative data from these interviews was systematically analysed and integrated with the findings from desk research to create a comprehensive view of the industry's regulatory environment. From interviews and documents thematic directions have emerged. These have also emerged as a matter of input to the research design and focal points that were combined with the documentation and interviews. The input of stakeholders, through workshops that have been conducted across the consortium, involving 15 participants from 6 European countries assisted in the first mapping of core issues in the regulatory, practice, normative and ethical dimensions of the governance of the gaming industry in Europe. Workshops to that effect took place between the period of September, October, and November resulting in over 9 hours of exchange. Specifically, the focus on topics such as diversity, inclusivity, youth protection and other social, cultural, and economic categories stems from their critical role in shaping the video game industry's potential to contribute to a broader societal impact. All interviews were conducted via video conferencing (zoom, teams) and followed a semi-structured format. Each interview lasted between 30 and 60 mins each. Questions focused on challenges facing the European video game industry, effectiveness of laws and regulations, policy and regulatory framework recommendations.

This report builds upon the discussions and insights gathered from previously organized workshops with experts and stakeholders, integrating their perspectives to inform its analysis and recommendations. Between April and June 2024, a series of workshops took place across Europe to discuss key issues and opportunities facing the Video Games Industry (VGI). These sessions, which involved over 41 participants from more than eight countries, provided a platform to examine the industry's challenges and explore pathways for sustainable growth. Each workshop focused on specific themes, reflecting the diversity of expertise and perspectives among the participating institutions. Discussions revolved around financial challenges, funding mechanisms, diversity, regulation, and policy measures which were utilised for this report (Bagnall et al., 2024).

The report provides a comparative analysis of national and EU-wide policies, aiming to identify opportunities and regulatory gaps. The analysis was informed by a diverse range of perspectives and focused on mapping trends in policy direction, implementation, and their broader socio-economic implications. Ethical considerations, particularly regarding diversity and inclusivity, were central to the research approach. Efforts were made to engage underrepresented groups and ensure the inclusion of their experiences and perspectives in both gaming communities and workplaces.

4. EU Legal Framework in the Video Games Industry

The video game industry in the European Union is expanding rapidly, contributing significantly to the cultural and digital economy. The sector encompasses a broad range of activities, including entertainment, education, and technological innovation, highlighting its pivotal role within the EU's digital strategy. These strategies strive to foster innovation while ensuring effective regulation across EU member states (Borgese, 2023).

One of the central concerns of video game regulation in the EU is consumer protection, particularly regarding practices that may exploit younger audiences. The Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (UCPD) aims to prevent deceptive practices and establishes rules for paid loot boxes in games, particularly regarding transparency and the disclosure of probabilities. This is particularly important in games aimed at children, where features similar to gambling-like mechanisms can blur the distinction between gaming and gambling.

The Digital Content Directive (DCD), Directive (EU) 2019/770, has significantly influenced consumer protection for digital goods, such as video games, across EU member states. Its main purpose is to harmonize digital content regulations within the European Union, prompting several member states to adjust their national consumer laws to comply with the directive's standards. In Germany, the DCD has been integrated into the national framework through updates to the "Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch" (BGB, German Civil Code). The law now mandates that digital products, including video games, must meet specific quality standards. If defects are found, consumers have the right to demand a repair, replacement, or refund (Bundesministerium der Justiz [BMJ], 2022). In France, the DCD has been incorporated into the "Code de la Consommation" (Consumer Code). French legislation grants consumers the right to withdraw from contracts for digital content if the product does not conform to expectations or has defects, a significant consideration for pre-ordered video games (Légifrance, 2021). In the Netherlands, national consumer laws have been adapted to meet the standards set by the DCD, emphasizing transparency in consumer rights. Dutch regulations now focus on the requirements for updates, repairs, and refunds for digital content, including video games, to ensure consistent protection (Netherlands Authority for Consumers & Markets, 2022). Therefore, while reports may focus on specific cases in countries like Poland, the DCD's impact is felt throughout the EU. The directive has established a more uniform framework for consumer protection related to digital goods, ensuring that core rights—such as the ability to request repairs or refunds—are upheld consistently across the European market (European Consumer Organisation, 2022).

Data protection is another critical regulatory area, with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) playing a significant role in the video game sector. GDPR ensures transparency in how players' data is used and restricts targeted advertising, especially for minors. Given that many video games collect detailed player data for profiling purposes, privacy concerns are a major issue, necessitating stringent regulations to safeguard personal information.

The presence of gambling-like elements in video games, such as loot boxes, has resulted in fragmented regulation across the EU member states. While the EU does not hold exclusive competence over gambling, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) has provided guidance on harmonising national laws to align with internal market principles. For instance, the CJEU has supported the European Commission's issuance of guidelines aimed at protecting consumers in the context of online gambling services, emphasising the need for consistent and effective consumer safeguards across the EU (European Gaming and Betting Association, n.d.). This ensures that gambling-like elements are regulated in a way that minimises harm to consumers while respecting the internal market. The European Union employs a distinctive and intricate governance system that significantly influences the regulation of online gaming within its member states. Rather than a single unified gambling law, each EU nation independently manages its gaming and gambling services, provided they adhere to the fundamental freedoms outlined in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU, n.d.). This results in variations in the scope of permissible online games across EU countries, highlighting the need for nuanced regulation in each member state (Scaleo, n.d.).

The protection of intellectual property (IP) is another important facet of video game regulation within the EU. The Copyright Directive, for example, ensures that video game developers retain the rights to their creations. These IP protections are vital for fostering innovation within the gaming industry by providing legal safeguards against unauthorised use or infringement of creative works (Grosheide, Roerdink, & Thomas, 2014). Furthermore, the EU emphasises the preservation of its cultural diversity, recognizing video games as a medium that not only entertains but also reflects the varied cultural identities of its member states. Video games are increasingly seen as cultural artefacts, highlighting the need to balance IP protection with the cultural heritage they represent (Harkai, 2022). This aligns with broader EU policies that aim to ensure diversity in digital content, supporting local and culturally distinctive game development (Feijóo, Nepelski, & De Prato, 2010). Moreover, the EU's IP laws are designed to facilitate cultural exchange within its borders while preventing cultural homogenization

that could result from dominant international players in the gaming market. This approach is intended to encourage the creation of games that reflect Europe's cultural richness and diversity. The EU's stance on digital games extends to state aid policies, which favour content that promotes local cultural values, showcasing a commitment to cultural sustainability alongside commercial interests (Graber & Burri, 2010).

Legal frameworks within the EU extend to various aspects of the gaming industry, including intellectual property rights and digital transactions. The EU has introduced specific directives that govern these digital interactions, aiming to enhance transparency and consumer protection. These measures are critical given the industry's digital nature, where transactions often involve intangible items like downloadable content and virtual assets (Demchenko, 2019). In addition to formal legislative frameworks, self-regulation plays a significant role in the video game sector. Initiatives such as PEGI and platform-specific codes of conduct help complement regulatory efforts, promoting a safer gaming environment for minors and enhancing consumer trust in the industry. The PEGI system is a voluntary, self-regulatory framework designed to assign age ratings and content descriptors to video games. This system helps inform parents and guardians about the appropriateness of games for children. PEGI also addresses concerns related to in-game purchases, including gambling-like elements, and provides information on online interactions, which can be crucial for ensuring a safe gaming experience for minors (Feci & Declerck, 2024). These self-regulatory mechanisms ensure that developers and publishers uphold ethical standards while offering entertainment to a wide audience.

Video game sector's expansion has prompted the EU to implement a range of regulations aimed at standardising content and protecting consumers across member states. One notable regulatory effort is the harmonisation of content classification through the Pan European Game Information (PEGI) system. PEGI is designed to provide uniform content warnings for video games, enabling informed decisions by consumers and parents about age-appropriate content (Robertson, 2008). This standardisation is part of a broader EU strategy to manage the cultural impact of video games while ensuring market cohesion.

The ongoing administration, monitoring, and development of the PEGI system have been entrusted to PEGI SA, an independent, private non-profit organisation with social objectives under Belgian law. The age rating serves as a recommendation to assist consumers in making informed purchasing decisions and is visible on the packaging of the respective game as well as in a database accessible on the PEGI website.

PEGI is used in 40 European countries including Austria, has 2,600 member companies, classified 40,000 games and millions of apps and is supported by the EU and major console manufacturers. 79% of parents with children that play video games are aware of the PEGI age rating labels, and 76% of them use the PEGI label to make an informed decision when considering buying a video game for their children (Video Games Europe, 2023).

5. Regulatory Trends and Divergences in the European Video Gaming Industry

The European video gaming industry, deeply embedded in modern culture and entertainment, is experiencing a dynamic evolution of regulatory landscapes. The European Union (EU) and other European nations are actively engaging in policy making to address the unique challenges posed by this rapidly growing sector, with a focus on consumer protection, data privacy, content regulation, and industry support. While unified frameworks exist in some areas, like age ratings through PEGI, national variation and divergence often lead to diverse approaches to vital issues such as minors' protection, loot boxes, and intellectual property.

5.1. Content Regulation and Age Classification

The PEGI (Pan European Game Information) system serves as a widely recognized standard for age classification in Europe. However, its enforcement varies significantly. For example, Germany's stricter content policies, which censor games with violent or Nazi symbols, due to historical reasons, contrast with the more liberal approaches of the UK and France, where PEGI ratings are largely respected with minimal intervention. This disparity challenges game developers as they navigate compliance with varying national regulations while striving to protect minors through responsible content ratings.

One prominent challenge is the fragmented regulatory approach to minors' data protection. Under GDPR, the age of consent varies across Europe, complicating developers' ability to transparently inform parents when consent is needed for data collection. Additionally, differing practices among platforms and developers regarding parental controls create inconsistencies, as no centralised regulatory approach ensures that age verification or parental controls are universally applied across platforms. Parental controls have been developed both by console manufacturers and by game publishers. The protection of minors from harmful content is a key regulatory concern in the gaming industry, which is addressed through systems like PEGI (Pan European Game Information n.d.) and its integration into the global IARC (International Age Rating Coalition) framework. Hence, while systems such as PEGI and IARC play a crucial role in protecting minors from potentially harmful content, the regulatory framework governing minors' online safety remains fragmented. This fragmentation presents challenges both for developers striving to comply with diverse regulations and for parents seeking to navigate an increasingly complex digital environment. To enhance the effectiveness of current efforts,

there is a need for more robust tools for age verification, as well as more cohesive and adaptable regulatory approach. Such a framework would better support the dynamic nature of the digital space, ensuring more consistent protections for children while fostering innovation and compliance in a rapidly evolving landscape.

Another key issue relates to the responsibility of different actors in the gaming value chain for protecting minors. There is ongoing debate about where the responsibility should lie, with platforms and operating systems often attempting to shift the burden onto game developers. The debate over ethical responsibility in the gaming industry often centers on whether game developers or gaming platforms should bear the primary burden. Some researchers suggest that ethical practices should be a shared responsibility, highlighting that platforms play a significant role in enforcing standards and setting the tone for ethical behavior within their ecosystems (Singh & Rizvi, 2023). In multiplayer and data-driven games, for example, platforms often influence ethical decision-making, yet developers are expected to align their practices with platform policies and user expectations (Seif El-Nasr & Kleinman, 2020; Sparrow, Gibbs, & Arnold, 2021). Additionally, platforms have a unique capacity to enforce ethical standards by controlling access to markets and technologies, making them key actors in fostering a culture of responsibility (Shilton & Greene, 2019; Lehtonen, Vesa, & Harviainen, 2022). This collaborative approach to ethics emphasizes the interconnected nature of modern game development.

In an interview with the Director of a Finnish game industry organisation, it was emphasised that the protection of minors involves multiple stakeholders, including regulatory bodies, platform holders, device manufacturers, and game developers. Cooperation among these parties is crucial, as responsibilities are distributed across different entities.

A significant regulatory gap exists in the enforcement of PEGI age ratings across different platforms and European countries. Although the PEGI system is mandatory in many European countries, some platforms like Steam and Apple do not support or prominently display these ratings, limiting transparency and making it harder for parents to make informed decisions. Closing this regulatory gap is crucial to ensuring that all platforms operating in Europe comply with PEGI and other European standards.

Finally, balancing minors' protection with artistic freedom and creativity is a complex issue. European regulators and the gaming industry need better models for balancing children's rights to privacy and protection from harmful content with the industry's creative output. Furthermore, empowering children through game creation and education is essential. This helps them understand the mechanics behind games, business models, and data usage, promoting media literacy and a deeper awareness of digital practices. Encouraging such active participation from children, in collaboration with policymakers and industry, will foster a better understanding of how games are made and consumed.

Beyond age ratings, PEGI also enforces a code of conduct that addresses issues such as Creating a safe gaming environment and ensures that game companies follow European legal frameworks, especially since many games played in Europe are produced outside the EU. This framework not only ensures adherence to local rules but also encourages companies to go beyond legal requirements for safer digital environments.

The debate over loot boxes in video games reflects broader regulatory divergences in Europe. The Netherlands consider loot boxes a form of gambling and impose strict regulations, while the UK and others adopt a self-regulatory approach. Industry experts advocate for a balanced stance that mitigates predatory practices without outright bans, suggesting measures like age restrictions and spending limits. The varying policies underscore the complex relationship between consumer protection, revenue models, and regulatory harmonisation across European markets.

We identified a significant funding challenge faced by the gaming industry, particularly in the context of the UK and across Europe. The current landscape of funding is marked by two primary issues: the impending conclusion of existing financial support systems and the need for enhanced investment. The UK currently operates two main funding mechanisms: the UK Games Fund, established in 2014-2015, which has provided over £13 million in support but will cease by the end of the next year, and the Video Games Tax Relief (VGTR), which has been instrumental for both small and large developers for over a decade. However, VGTR is being replaced by the Video Games Expenditure Credit (Video Games Europe Credit), which will become the sole form of tax relief in the UK. The VGTR was a pioneering initiative that attracted significant investment into the UK gaming sector, but its effectiveness has diminished as other countries, such as Canada, France, Germany, and Ireland, have introduced more appealing tax reliefs or have improved the existing regulations.

The industry is advocating for the UK government to reassess the structure of its tax relief, aiming to increase its effective rate, which has remained stagnant in recent years. Overall, the funding landscape poses significant challenges for the UK gaming industry, necessitating a strategic review of funding mechanisms to remain competitive with other European nations.

A key concern of stakeholders, as explained to us by our interviewees, is the potential over-regulation of in-app purchases, which could severely impact the mobile gaming business. Many reports and regulatory discussions propose bans or severe restrictions on in-app purchases due to their association with predatory practices, particularly regarding loot boxes. However, current academic commentary on the legal challenges of regulating loot boxes accepts that no single regulatory approach is likely to provide suitable, consistently effective solutions for the psychological, social, and financial risks of interaction with the format (Derrington et al., 2021; Xiao, 2021). Difficulties for legislators are compounded by the essentially quasi-gambling structure of game design, the current stage of research into risks, associated harms, and the time lags between game development, research outputs, and substantive evidence of harm (Leahy, 2022, p.562). In 2020, the Committee on Internal Market and Consumer Protection (IMCO Committee) of the EU Parliament requested a study to investigate loot boxes in online games and their effects on consumers, especially young consumers. The objective of this study was to identify measures which could improve the regulation of loot boxes in the EU, for which several strategies were recommended (Cerulli-Harms et al., 2020).

In recent years, the gaming industry has faced significant scrutiny over in-app purchases, particularly due to concerns about potential over-regulation and predatory practices such as loot boxes. Stakeholders in the gaming sector express concerns that stringent regulation could harm the mobile gaming market by restricting the flexibility of developers to monetize games (Jull Sørensen, Rott, & Sein, 2023). Over-regulation poses a threat to innovation and could hinder the industry's economic contributions, especially in regions reliant on the gaming sector for digital economic growth (Lee & Schiöler, 2019). In parallel, numerous regulatory bodies and consumer protection advocates have highlighted the risks associated with in-app purchases, particularly loot boxes, which are often compared to gambling due to their randomized reward systems (Leahy, 2022). These elements have led to calls for stricter regulatory measures, aiming to protect vulnerable consumers from potentially exploitative practices (Egielski, 2021). As the debate continues, finding a balance between protecting consumers and maintaining a thriving digital economy remains a complex challenge for policymakers and the gaming industry.

A growing body of professionals within the industry argues for a more nuanced approach, emphasizing the importance of consulting experts to distinguish between exploitative practices and those that align with ethical standards. A pertinent example of this approach is the Pan-European Game Information (PEGI) system, which has implemented more transparent age ratings and content descriptors to inform consumers about games that include loot boxes. This strategy effectively addresses public concerns while avoiding the imposition of blanket prohibitions (PEGI, n.d.). Similarly, Electronic Arts (EA) has engaged in dialogue with regulators and consumer advocacy groups to implement transparency measures, such as disclosing loot box odds and providing parental control tools, which aim to reduce potential harm while preserving monetization flexibility (Electronic Arts, 2022). These initiatives demonstrate how collaborative efforts between industry leaders and regulatory bodies can create ethical solutions that protect consumers without stifling innovation.

There is broad non-industry support for solutions aimed at reducing the predatory nature of loot boxes without resorting to extreme regulatory actions like outright bans (Zendle & Cairns, 2019; King et al., 2022). Proposed measures include setting age restrictions, such as an 18+ rating for games containing loot boxes, and implementing spending limits to promote consumer awareness. For instance, players could be notified about their spending behaviour, as many are unaware of how much they actually spend.

Makena Kelly (2019) provides a nuanced view, showing how bans might address the exploitation of vulnerable consumers while posing challenges for regulatory uniformity across borders. The case of Belgium illustrates the feasibility of banning loot boxes, as gaming companies either redesigned their mechanics or withdrew from the market. This contrasts sharply with countries like the UK, where bans are absent, and regulatory bodies have adopted a “wait-and-watch” approach. Further, Xiao et al. (2022) emphasize that bans, while effective in reducing harm, might not be the most sustainable solution. Instead, they advocate for regulatory measures such as limiting spending, enhancing transparency through probability disclosures, and modifying loot box designs to reduce addictive behaviors. This balanced approach allows for consumer protection without resorting to the most extreme regulatory measures, such as complete prohibitions. By leveraging such harm-reduction strategies, regulators can address the underlying issues of financial and psychological harm without the unintended consequences of outright bans.

The current regulatory perspective on loot boxes in video games suggests that the industry is not significantly alarmed by potential legislative changes, especially because many systems are designed for individuals aged 18 and older, thus mitigating concerns related to the protection of minors. This strategy reflects a calculated approach by game developers to address public and regulatory concerns while continuing profitable monetization practices. However, such self-regulation may still face scrutiny as debates surrounding consumer ethics and the gambling-like elements of these games continue to evolve (Feci & Declerck, 2024). Research indicates that the gaming industry often self-regulates by adopting measures that promote transparency and consumer protection, aiming to prevent stricter legal oversight. For example, studies show that loot boxes, while controversial at times, are structured in a way that minimizes direct exposure to younger audiences (European Parliament, 2020).

An additional example relates to the incorporation of blockchain elements in games. Initially, there was interest in exploring blockchain technology for its potential to enhance player ownership and asset transfer. Blockchain technology in games provides players with true digital ownership, allowing in-game assets to be securely and transparently traded without intermediaries. It also enables players to convert their in-game achievements into real-world economic value through smart contracts and NFTs.

However, France's sudden classification of blockchain-based games as gambling has necessitated compliance with gambling regulations, hindering innovation in this area. France's classification of blockchain-based games as gambling occurred in June 2023, when the French National Gambling Authority (Autorité Nationale des Jeux, ANJ) issued guidance indicating that certain blockchain-based games, particularly those involving non-fungible tokens (NFTs) and play-to-earn (P2E) models, could fall under gambling regulations. This decision was based on concerns over the speculative nature of these games, which often involve real-money stakes and rewards, aligning them with gambling activities.

In our exploration of the regulatory landscape surrounding loot boxes, we found that the topic has garnered varied attention across the UK and Europe. In 2019, the UK government initiated an inquiry into loot box practices, leading the Culture, Media and Sport Select Committee to agree in 2021 that the gaming industry would engage in self-regulation. This process included the establishment of a working group tasked with developing best practices for loot box management, intended to apply not only within the UK but also on a global scale. After a year of collaborative efforts, a set of 11 to 12 non-mandatory recommendations was published in

June 2022 (Xiao et al., 2022). The recommendations were a response to growing concerns about the potential gambling-like nature of loot boxes, as well as their impact on children and vulnerable groups (Pour, 2024). Research has highlighted that while self-regulation is a promising step, compliance remains inconsistent across the gaming industry, particularly in disclosing loot box probabilities (Hodge, McAlaney, & Bush-Evans, 2022). Comparative studies have indicated that regulatory frameworks vary globally, but the UK model has been influential in shaping international policy discourse. (Grimes & Jayemanne, 2023).

The UK government is currently assessing the impact of these practices on the UK gaming industry and has indicated that it may intervene with regulation if significant improvements are not observed. Despite the initial enthusiasm surrounding this issue, recent discussions suggest that loot boxes have diminished as a priority on the UK government's agenda. In contrast, the topic remains highly relevant within the EU, where regulatory frameworks are still evolving.

5.2. Data Protection and Privacy

Data protection is another area where regulatory practices diverge, albeit within the framework of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). While GDPR sets a baseline for data protection across the EU, national interpretations and enforcement can differ. For instance, France's CNIL (Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés) is known for its rigorous enforcement of data protection laws, leading to hefty fines for non-compliance. In contrast, other countries may take a more lenient approach, focusing on guidance and compliance rather than punitive measures. These differences can create varying levels of risk for gaming companies operating across multiple jurisdictions.

Through our interviews with stakeholders, we identified the importance of integrating children's rights into video game design was underscored. Children often engage with video games from a young age, and while research shows potential benefits (Granic et al., 2014; Campos & Fernandez, 2016), there are also serious risks involved. Video games can become excessively captivating, potentially harming children's well-being and exposing them to privacy risks (Stoilova et al., 2021). It is crucial to consider both the risks and benefits of video games during the design phase.

5.3. Consumer Protection and Industry Incentives

Consumer protection in gaming is another area with divergent national approaches. Finland, for example, along with Belgium and Netherlands, places a strong emphasis on transparency and fair-trade practices within its consumer protection laws, requiring detailed information on in-game purchases and refund policies. This contrasts with other nations, e.g. Austria, France, Italy, Spain, where consumer protection focuses more narrowly on specific aspects like refund rights without delving into the transparency of in-game transactions.

Regarding industry incentives, Poland provides a case study in government support for the video game sector through initiatives like the GameINN program, which offers financial support for innovation in game development. This proactive approach contrasts with countries where government support is less direct, focusing instead on tax incentives or general creative industry grants.

5.4. Intellectual Property and Cultural Diversity

The protection of intellectual property (IP) and the promotion of cultural diversity are also critical areas of divergence. The EU's Digital Single Market strategy aims to harmonise IP laws and promote cultural diversity across member states. However, national implementations can differ, particularly in how they support local content creation. For example, Austria's commitment to promoting cultural diversity in video games is reflected in its support for diverse content creation through funding programmes, a practice that may not be as pronounced in other European countries.

In an interview with an employee from a game publishing company, we explored the gaming industry's contributions to society and the economy, both in France and across Europe. It is evident that the impact is largely similar across European nations. There are several facets to consider. First, video games engage the imaginations of millions worldwide, transcending national markets. A video game is designed for a global audience, emphasising universality over localised content. Therefore, a well-crafted video game developed in Europe has the potential to resonate with audiences everywhere. With approximately 3 billion players globally, predominantly among younger generations, video games serve as a medium for

cultural expression and soft power. They effectively capture and inspire the imaginations of people. Moreover, the gaming sector operates at the intersection of culture, technology, and innovation, positioning it as a primary gateway to digital experiences for many. For the youth, video games often mark the beginning of their digital lives, introducing them to various technologies and collaborative practices that will shape their future interactions in the digital realm. Economically, the gaming industry encompasses a diverse array of job roles involved in creating a single game, ranging from technology and design to sound and game development. This multifaceted approach illustrates the industry's role as a "factory" for the digital landscape, reflecting the increasing digitization of our lives and highlighting the importance of video games in shaping this new universe.

6. Regulating the Video Game Industry in European Countries: A Comparative Overview

The gaming industry in Europe has evolved into a multifaceted sector that transcends its original role as a source of entertainment. Today, it represents a crucial contributor to the European economy, and to innovation, creativity, and cultural identity. The industry has emerged as a significant force in job creation, technological advancements, and creative expression, with Europe establishing itself as a leading hub for game development and publishing on the global stage. From independent studios to major game development companies, Europe hosts a vibrant ecosystem that is shaping the future of interactive digital experiences.

The industry's reach extends well beyond its economic impact. Millions of players from diverse demographic backgrounds engage with video games, rendering video games not only a source of leisure, but also a tool for social interaction, cultural and self-expression, education, and participation in immersive digital storytelling. Video games, as a form of media, are increasingly recognised for their potential to bridge cultural divides, foster community, and even address societal issues through creative narratives. This growing recognition has placed the gaming industry at the intersection of technology, art, and culture.

A combination of popularity of video games, technological advancement, games development trends and marketisation and monetisation strategies has made the need for effective regulatory frameworks pressing. Policymakers across Europe are increasingly called to focus on safeguarding consumers, with particular attention to the protection of children and youth and attending to issues of addiction, as two core and urgent societal concerns. Meanwhile, the industry overall is interested in promoting responsible gaming practices and commercial growth as part of Europe's creative sector. regulations aim to protect players, especially younger audiences, from risks like addiction and inappropriate content, while also encouraging innovation and international competitiveness within the industry.

Given the analyses carried out there are notable commonalities in the regulatory approaches adopted by most European nations, including those countries analysed in detail in this report: Austria, the Netherlands, Poland, and the UK. These countries have each implemented policies aimed at safeguarding consumer rights, promoting industry transparency, and supporting the sustainable growth of the gaming industry. For instance, in all of these countries' policies the importance of age-appropriate content, data protection, and the regulation of

microtransactions, particularly in games that are accessible to children are emphasised. Additionally, there is a shared recognition of the importance of fostering the development of local talent and supporting indie game developers as part of broader cultural and economic strategies. The European video gaming industry is marked by a diverse regulatory landscape, with each country taking its own approach to balancing industry growth, consumer protection, and social responsibility. While there are some overarching EU directives that unify certain aspects of regulation, significant divergences exist, particularly in areas such as content regulation, data protection, consumer protection, industry incentives, and the regulation of emerging phenomena like loot boxes.

In this section, we explore the national initiatives across Austria, Finland, the Netherlands, Poland, and the United Kingdom, focusing on key policy areas: age classification and content regulation, data protection under frameworks such as GDPR, consumer protection measures addressing issues like loot boxes, and intellectual property laws. The report further examines themes of cultural diversity promotion, gender and minority representation, and strategies to balance youth protection with fostering industry growth. The discussion also addresses regulatory disparities, challenges in harmonising EU and national policies, and approaches to enhancing innovation and sustainability in the video game ecosystem.

6.1 Austria

The gaming and eSports sector in Austria is a rapidly growing industry, with a community of 5.3 million gamers and an annual revenue of \$24.1 million (Data from ÖVUS/GfK, 2019; ESVÖ, A1, & Nielsen, 2019; WKO, UBIT, BMDW, Pioneers, & IWI, 2019). This market has become a significant contributor to the digital economy. However, the industry also faces legislative challenges that must be addressed.

In Austria, each of the nine states, or “Bundesländer,” operates under a federal system that delineates powers between the national government and the states themselves. The Austrian Constitution grants states the authority to legislate and manage matters such as education, local law enforcement, health care, and cultural affairs. This decentralised approach allows each state to address its unique needs and preferences while adhering to overarching national laws. However, this approach makes implementation of youth protection laws even

more challenging. According to Article 15 (1) of the Federal Constitutional Law (B-VG), youth protection in legislation and enforcement is the responsibility of the individual states, leading to a lack of uniform federal regulations at the basic legislative level. Instead, the individual states are encouraged to establish adequate protective mechanisms.

Consumer protection

The regulation of video games is primarily focused on content classification and consumer protection, reflecting broader European practices in Austria. While these practices align with EU values and some member-state policies, they are not legally binding across Europe. PEGI, for instance, is recognized as a guideline and widely adopted, but its enforcement depends on individual member states or private organisations (De Haan, 2013).

The “Unterhaltungssoftware Selbstkontrolle” – USK² (Entertainment Software Self-Regulation Body), the Pan European Game Information (PEGI) and the „Freiwillige Selbstkontrolle der Filmwirtschaft – FSK (Voluntary Self Regulation of the Movie Industry) aim to prevent children and adolescents from accessing series, computer games, and films that are inappropriate for their respective age groups.

The ongoing digitalisation and rapidly expanding video games industry often leads to heated debates about youth protection and universal regulation (Galwey, 2024; Singh & Balhara, 2023). In 2023, the debate was held by the European Parliament’s plenary sitting in Strasbourg on consumer protection in online video games. The resolution highlighted the risks to children and minors in online games and the sexual objectification, among other issues e.g. sexual objectification of women in video games (European Parliament, 2023). With “73% of children aged 6-10, 84% of those aged 11-14 and 74% of young people aged 15-24 playing video games” (European Commission, 2022, p. 7). The document highlights the issue of inadequate consumer protection mechanisms at the European level. In particular, children are misled into making in-game purchases while the gambling-like effect of loot boxes, which involve spending real money on items, can lead to addiction. While the consumption and distribution of video games predominantly take place online, this presents additional challenges for implementing any form of regulation.

2 The organisation responsible for video game ratings in Germany. In Austria, it is mandatory in the state of Salzburg, while PEGI is mandatory in Vienna.

Austrian legal frameworks, regulatory mechanisms, and international standards govern the area of youth protection in relation to video games and is governed by a range of national and EU laws. The Jugendschutzgesetz (Youth Protection Act) regulates age-appropriate content for minors, while the Verbraucherschutzgesetz (Consumer Protection Act) ensures consumer rights, including those related to digital games. Additionally, the EU Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD) provides guidelines on media content for minors, and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) safeguards the personal data of individuals, especially minors, in digital spaces (European Commission, 2024; European Union, 2024; GDPR, 2024).

However, Austrian youth protection laws are considered too complex and too ambiguous with challenges of evolving standards, and constitutional concerns surrounding the delegation of norm-setting authority to private organisations.

Austria's youth protection framework is based on both national legislation and EU-level policies that aim to safeguard young people from harm while encouraging personal responsibility. The Jugendgesetz (Youth Act) at the federal and regional levels, together with the EU Youth Strategy and the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), form the legal basis for these dual objectives. Therefore, the youth protection framework in Austria is aligned with the European Union's youth policy, which emphasizes both protection and empowerment (European Union, 2012; Republik Österreich, 2019).

Currently, Austria does not have its own age classification system for computer games. Nevertheless, the "Bundesstelle für die Positivprädikatisierung von digitalen Spielen im Bundeskanzleramt" (federal office for the positive rating of digital gaming in the federal chancellery, BuPP - www.bupp.at) is a national institution whose jurisdiction is the oversight of content in computer games. It is an advisory institution that provides information on recommended computer games to offer parents and educators guidance in their selection. According to Article 14 (5a) of the Federal Constitutional Law (B-VG), in the collaborative interaction of students, parents, and teachers, the aim is to enable children and adolescents to achieve the best possible mental, emotional, and physical development. This law emphasises the importance of working together to support the growth and well-being of young individuals. In practice, the age rating systems of PEGI and USK have become established to warn underage consumers and their guardians about age inappropriate and potentially harmful

content. These systems do not stop children from accessing this content and generally accessing computer games that are deemed unsuitable for their respective age groups. PEGI (Pan European Game Information) and USK (Unterhaltungssoftware Selbstkontrolle) differ significantly in their structure and role within Europe's game rating landscape. PEGI is a private, industry-driven rating system established by the Interactive Software Federation of Europe (ISFE) to provide age-based content ratings across most European countries. Although PEGI collaborates with public bodies and is supported by the EU, it operates as an independent, self-regulatory system, providing age recommendations rather than restrictions. USK, in contrast, is Germany's official game rating body and functions as an authoritative body under German law. While also funded by the gaming industry, USK works closely with German government authorities, following legally binding guidelines and requiring that games sold in Germany carry an official USK rating. This regulatory integration makes USK unique to Germany, where its ratings are a legal requirement, whereas PEGI operates across Europe as a broadly accepted standard, which, depending on the country, has been integrated and recognised into their national law. USK is the final stage of the testing process (age rating) is carried out by an official administrative act of the German Supreme State Youth Authorities according to § 14 (2) of the German Youth Protection Act. Austrian youth protection laws also aim to counteract potential dangers arising from the content of computer games. To address this, media protection norms have been integrated into regional youth protection laws, defining sources of danger. Notably, only the regional laws of Salzburg and Vienna make additional references to age rating systems: Protection of Minors. (n.d.). Section 38 (2) of the Salzburg Youth Act refers to the German USK system, while Section 10 (3) of the Vienna Youth Protection Act refers to the standards of PEGI.

In an interview conducted with the Austrian Association for Gaming, the need for standardised PEGI ratings across Austria was noted, given the existing provincial variations in age restriction laws. Video game age restrictions in Austria vary from province to province, which can lead to disparities in the way games are evaluated and marketed in the nation. The main issue is that different states (Bundesländer) have some degree of autonomy over media regulation, including video games, which results in varying interpretations and applications of age restrictions. For instance, age restrictions for games with violent or sexual material may be more strictly enforced in some areas than in others, and PEGI ratings may not always be applied or entirely aligned with. Additionally, parental involvement was highlighted as essential to effective youth protection, as parents are encouraged to use available safeguards on gaming platforms.

Diversity

Broader EU directives and policies provide Austria with guidelines to promote diversity in video games. EU Digital Single Market strategy is one initiative that seeks to ensure that digital content, including video games, reflects the diversity of European cultures (Burri, 2017).

Nationally, the commitment to diversity in media, including video games, is enshrined in several legal instruments. Bundesministerium für Kunst, Kultur, öffentlichen Dienst und Sport (*The Austrian Federal Ministry of Arts, Culture, Civil Service and Sport*) is responsible for promoting cultural diversity, including funding programs that support diverse content creation in video games. The EU Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD), implemented in Austria, also mandates that audiovisual content, including video games, should adhere to principles of cultural diversity and non-discrimination (Breemen & Vianello, 2021). Furthermore, the Austrian Federal Act on Equal Treatment ensures that any discriminatory practices within the video game industry, whether in employment or in content production, are prohibited. This act applies to video game companies operating within Austria, requiring that diversity is upheld not only in the workplace, but also in the games they produce (Kennedy & Dovey, 2014).

Data Protection & Age Ratings

Data protection in the video game industry is governed by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which is also applicable across all EU member states. The GDPR sets stringent requirements for the collection, processing, and storage of personal data, directly impacting how video game companies operate (De Hert & Papakonstantinou, 2012). The Digital Services Act (DSA) primarily focuses on the regulation of digital services, platforms, and online intermediaries, rather than directly addressing data protection. However, it does indirectly affect data protection by imposing transparency and accountability measures, particularly regarding content moderation and user interactions. In contrast, data protection in the European Union is governed by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and national laws like the Austrian Data Protection Act (DSG), which outline the handling of personal data, including safeguards for minors in the digital realm. The DSG is an Austrian law and contains provisions supplementing the GDPR as well as regulations implementing Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on

the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security, as well as for the purposes of national security, intelligence and military self-defence. It also includes specific provisions for the protection of minors in digital environments (Gutwirth, Leenes, & De Hert, 2015).

Unlike the GDPR, which allows EU member states to lower the age threshold for requiring parental consent from 16 to 13, the Austrian DSG sets the threshold at 14 years, in line with Austrian civil law provisions (DSG, Art. 2, p.2). This means minors aged 14 and above can provide valid consent for data processing without parental involvement in Austria. For minors under 14, the DSG explicitly requires verifiable parental or guardian consent for any data processing activities, especially in online services like video games or social media platforms. The DSG reinforces GDPR's data minimisation principle, requiring service providers to limit the collection, processing, and storage of minors' data strictly to what is necessary for providing their service. While the GDPR broadly limits automated decision-making, the DSG places additional restrictions on profiling minors, particularly when it could result in high-risk outcomes like exclusion or discrimination. Also, the DSG requires that privacy policies and notices provided to minors must be easily understandable, using language and formats suitable for younger audiences (DSB, 2024).

In Austria, the implementation of GDPR is overseen by the Austrian Data Protection Authority (Datenschutzbehörde), which ensures compliance with principles such as data minimization, purpose limitation, and the protection of data subjects' rights. Video game companies must obtain explicit consent from users for data collection, provide clear information on data usage, and ensure the security of personal data (Nissenbaum, 2011).

6.2 Finland

Finland's gaming industry has approximately 2.8 million gamers with approximately 30% being women, generating \$797.3 million in annual revenue (Statista, 2020). Video games are covered under a wide range of regulations that encompass gaming laws in Finland. These laws and regulations are designed to ensure that consumers are protected and ensure fair play. In addition, they are in place to regulate the industry. Just like many other European countries, Finland uses the PEGI System for age ratings. Video games that are sold in Finland

have to display the appropriate PEGI rating to educate the consumers about the suitability of the content in the game. Content restriction also ensures that games that are considered inappropriate or harmful for minors are restricted. This includes sexual content, explicit violence, and other mature themes.

Consumer protection

There is a proposed bill to regulate loot boxes as a form of gambling in the Finnish Parliament (Menmuir, 2024). In 2027, Finland will transition from its gambling monopoly to a regulated licensing system, allowing private operators for online betting and casino games. A new regulatory authority will enforce compliance, with restrictions on marketing and supervision of operators (Ek & Karpathakis, 2024).

In an interview with a Senior Policy Analyst from Finland, it was highlighted that, while certain challenges are common across European countries, Finland encounters distinct issues. Notably, while Finland provides robust R&D (research and experimental development) funding for the video game industry, which has established the nation as a hub, a significant gap exists in production funding. The absence of grants or tax incentives at the stage of production poses a barrier to marketisation. Hence, support for the video game industry involves two distinct but interconnected matters. First, Finland offers substantial funding for technological advancement and game development in early stages. However, the second issue arises from the lack of adequate production funding. This gap creates a barrier for game developers who, despite having strong research and technological capabilities, may struggle to secure the financial backing required to bring their projects to the market. These two points are related in that the absence of production funding undermines the benefits of the R&D investment. Developers may find it difficult to move from the research and innovation phase to full-scale game production, limiting their ability to capitalise on the talent and technology being cultivated in the country. The funding shortfall thus affects the overall sustainability and growth of the industry in Finland, despite the strong initial advantages provided by R&D. Finland has been uniquely committed to targeted funding initiatives since 1998, primarily aimed at business development and R&D. The Finnish government allocates approximately €2.3 million towards research and development yearly, with preliminary estimated €2.5 million to be invested in 2024 (Statistics Finland, 2024).

Data Protection & Age Ratings

Transparency in the gaming industry is essential for fostering trust between game publishers, consumers, and developers. In Finland, game developers are required to provide clear and detailed information about their products. This includes comprehensive descriptions of the game content, such as genre, gameplay mechanics, age-appropriate ratings, and potential in-game interactions. Additionally, transparency about pricing is crucial; this means not only the upfront cost of purchasing a game, but also the detailed breakdown of any additional costs associated with in-game purchases. These can include microtransactions, downloadable content (DLC), and subscription services.

Under Finnish consumer protection laws, Finland Consumer Protection Act refund policies play a critical role in protecting consumer rights within the gaming industry. These laws ensure that consumers receive and are entitled to refunds for products that fail to meet reasonable expectations or are defective. This is particularly relevant in the context of digital games, where performance problems, bugs, and misrepresented content can affect the user experience. If a purchased game is defective, malfunctions or deviates from the advertised experience it qualifies for a refund.

The Finnish Consumer Protection Act (CPA) ensures transparency in the gaming industry, particularly in the areas of game content, pricing, and consumer rights regarding refunds. Game developers and publishers must provide clear information about their products, including detailed descriptions of gameplay, pricing structures (e.g., in-game purchases, DLC, and subscriptions), and any age or content restrictions. This adherence to transparency aligns with the goals of the CPA, which seeks to ensure that consumers can make informed purchasing decisions (Roschier, 2022). Moreover, the CPA enforces consumer protection rights in the event of defective or non-conforming products, including digital goods like video games. If a game fails to meet the expected standards or functionality, consumers are entitled to remedies such as repair, replacement, price reduction, or a full refund. These provisions apply to both physical and digital products, ensuring that consumers are protected against products that do not meet reasonable expectations (Waselius & Partners, 2022). Furthermore, developers and publishers are legally required to adhere to these standards to ensure that consumers' rights are upheld under Finnish law (Finlex, n.d.).

In alignment with the GDPR enforced across the EU, Finland mandates that game companies adhere to stringent standards regarding the handling of user data. These regulations require that game companies collect, store, and process personal data lawfully, ensuring full transparency and security. Companies must inform users about the kind of data being collected, the purpose of its collection, and how it will be used. Consent must be explicit and informed, with users having the right to withdraw their consent at any time. Additionally, robust measures must be implemented to protect data from breaches and unauthorised access.

Diversity

The Non-Discrimination and the Equality Act in Finland (2014), is established to ensure equality and prevent discrimination based on factors such as age, gender, ethnicity, disability, and sexual orientation, and extends its influence into the video gaming industry. The Act mandates that gaming companies operating within Finland must foster inclusive environments both within their organisational culture and in the content they produce. This means that hiring practices, workplace policies, and career advancement opportunities must be free from bias, providing equal opportunities for all individuals. Additionally, the Act encourages developers to create games that are inclusive and accessible, reflecting diverse characters and stories to resonate with a broad audience. By adhering to these principles, the Finnish gaming industry not only complies with national legal standards, but also contributes to a more equitable and diverse global gaming community. The Finnish CPA encourages game developers to create products that are transparent, inclusive, and accessible, ensuring that games feature diverse characters and narratives. This reflects a commitment to fairness and equity, which helps developers create games that resonate with a broad audience (Roschier, 2022). By adhering to these standards, Finnish developers not only meet national legal requirements but also contribute to a global gaming community that values diversity, representation, and accessibility. This ethical approach has influenced the broader gaming industry, with major international developers like Ubisoft and Electronic Arts focusing more on inclusivity in their games. These companies are increasingly incorporating diverse characters and storylines, following similar principles of inclusivity and accessibility, as promoted by Finnish consumer protection standards (Waselius & Partners, 2022).

Compounding that, an identified shortage of skilled employees remains a pressing issue for the sector, as emphasised by the Director of a prominent Finnish game industry organisation. Despite the availability of numerous educational programmes across Europe, from bachelor

and master programmes in the leading European Universities to graduate programmes set up by the industry leaders, e.g. Ubisoft Graduate Program, to specialised bootcamps and workshops, a significant gap in senior talent continues to challenge the industry. This shortage is exacerbated by the gaming sector's rapid expansion, consistently heightening the demand for experienced professionals.

6.3. Netherlands

The Netherlands has a thriving gaming industry, with an estimated 10 million gamers generating a substantial revenue of \$3.21 billion annually (Dutch Games Association). In 2020, women made up about 47% of the Dutch gaming population, with significant interest in casual mobile gaming and puzzle-based games (Dutch Video Games Industry, 2020).

A comprehensive regulatory framework of policies that govern the video game industry has been established in the Netherlands. Similar to other European countries these policies cover a wide range of aspects, including consumer protection, content regulation, age rating and the promotion and support of the cultural and creative industries of game development.

Data Protection & Age Ratings

The regulation of video games follows European wide standards. While PEGI provides the age-rating system, the regulation of video games in the Netherlands is a multi-stakeholder process involving industry, government, and consumer advocacy groups, all working together within both national and European frameworks. and involves different stakeholders such as industry bodies, government agencies, and consumer organisations

According to Dutch law the distribution of games with harmful or inappropriate content for minors is prohibited including sexual content, hate speech and explicit violence. The Dutch Media Authority (Commissariaat voor de Media) is responsible for enforcing and overseeing these regulations. In the Netherlands, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) implemented across the European Union, governs how video games companies store, process and collect personal data to ensure that players' privacy rights are protected.

Consumer protection

The regulatory approach to loot boxes in video games has indeed been highly contentious, with many arguing that the way regulators have handled the issue is chaotic and inconsistent. In the case of the Netherlands, the country initially emerged as a leader in addressing loot boxes by attempting to regulate them under existing gambling laws. However, this effort has been marred by legal ambiguities, divergent open interpretations of norms, and a lack of clear, updated legislation, leading to a fragmented regulatory landscape.

In the Netherlands, loot boxes have been scrutinised under the legal framework that defines gambling. Specifically, the Dutch Gambling Authority relies on an “open norm” to determine what constitutes a game of chance. According to this standard, if a game allows players to win prizes or premiums, and those prizes are determined by chance rather than skill, the game can be classified as gambling. This open-ended definition has been a point of debate, as it allows for a wide range of interpretations and, in many cases, does not adequately account for the complexities of modern gaming.

The open norm used by the Dutch Gambling Authority to define a “game of chance” has led to diverse interpretations, especially concerning loot boxes in modern video games. This standard, which considers a game as gambling if prizes are awarded by chance rather than skill, has generated debate because it does not fully capture the complexity of digital games. Many contemporary games blend elements of skill and chance, making it difficult to categorise them strictly as gambling. For example, while loot boxes involve a chance-based mechanism to obtain in-game items, they are often integrated into skill-based gameplay, progression, and competition. Additionally, the legal framework does not clearly address the psychological impact of these mechanics or the dynamics of virtual economies, which involve virtual goods with real-world value. This ambiguity has resulted in inconsistent regulatory actions and uncertainty for developers and players, reflecting the challenge of applying traditional gambling definitions to modern interactive media (Macey & Hamari, 2019; Nielsen & Grabarczyk, 2019).

Rather than introducing new, specific legislation to address loot boxes, Dutch regulators have extended a generic gambling norm to the gaming industry. The immediate effect of this policy has been legal challenges by and uncertainty for game developers. For instance, Electronic

Arts (EA) faced penalties after its FIFA series was found to include loot boxes that violated these gambling regulations. While EA appealed, the case clarified that loot boxes could be seen as standalone games of chance, which complicates the legal landscape for similar in-game mechanics in other titles.

Overall, the Dutch government actively promotes the gaming industry through various initiatives aimed at bolstering the cultural and creative economy. The Creative Industries Fund NL n.d. provides grants specifically for innovation in digital storytelling and interactive media, including video games. This approach supports the development of culturally significant content and enables smaller studios to gain a foothold in the market.

The Netherlands has also displayed policy leadership around sustainability in the gaming industry, emphasising responsible energy use and digital carbon footprints (United Nations Environment Programme). For instance, projects like STRATEGIES (Sustainable Transition for Europe's Game Industries) aim to guide the European gaming industry towards a sustainable future. This initiative has a dual focus: reducing the ecological footprint of game development, distribution, and consumption, and fostering the use of ecogames to engage diverse audiences in climate crisis awareness and sustainability. By encouraging "greener" gaming practices, such as minimising greenhouse gas emissions, STRATEGIES positions the industry to both lessen its environmental impact and act as a catalyst for environmental consciousness among players. The initiative, closely associated with Utrecht University's research on ecogames, underscores the potential of video games as influential tools for promoting sustainable behaviours and perspectives (Gameresearch, 2024).

Diversity

The Dutch Gambling Authority's method of utilising an open norm to determine gambling allows for a flexible, case-by-case assessment of digital gaming, which, although controversial, provides a dynamic regulatory framework adaptable to the rapidly evolving gaming landscape. This regulatory flexibility is paired with robust collaborations between government bodies, academic institutions, and industry stakeholders, fostering a research-informed policy environment. Furthermore, the Netherlands supports a culturally vibrant gaming sector by encouraging the development of ecogames and games that promote social awareness,

enhancing the potential of video games as educational and ethical platforms. By integrating sustainability with innovation and regulation, the Netherlands is not only safeguarding consumers but also shaping a future-forward, resilient gaming industry that aligns with broader societal goals, such as environmental stewardship and responsible digital consumption (van Looy, 2022; VGFN, 2023).

This comprehensive approach demonstrates the Netherlands' commitment to creating a responsible, sustainable, and consumer-protective regulatory environment for the gaming industry, while fostering an innovative and culturally vibrant sector. The Cultural Monitor report highlights the importance of inclusivity and social safety within cultural sectors, emphasizing accessibility for disabled individuals, institutional power dynamics, and decolonization efforts. The Dutch government invests heavily in cultural diversity initiatives, supporting projects like commemorations of the country's slavery history. Such initiatives enhance cultural richness and foster a more inclusive narrative within the gaming sector (Cultuurmonitor, 2024). There has been increasing recognition of the importance of diversity and inclusion within the gaming industry. Recent surveys have provided valuable insights into gender, age, foreign talent, and policy measures. Over the past few years, the percentage of women in game companies has steadily increased, reaching 23% in 2021, along with rising representation of non-binary, gender-fluid, and transgender individuals. Additionally, the average age of professionals in the industry is rising, with a growing number of veterans contributing to its evolution. Historically, video games were viewed as predominantly men-oriented, but today they appeal to a much broader audience, with a nearly equal split between male and female players. The industry is aiming to be more inclusive, with greater diversity in the workforce, though this transition is gradual. Gender distribution has been a focus of attention for several years. In 2012, the proportion of women in game companies was estimated at 13.5%, which increased to 23% by 2021. The student population is also becoming more diverse, which could further influence gender distribution in the future.

More women are also stepping into leadership roles, with several major gaming companies appointing female CEOs in recent years. While the number of people identifying as non-binary remains low, awareness of this issue is growing, and there is an increasing number of individuals in the industry identifying as non-binary, genderqueer, gender-fluid, or transgender. The average age of employees in the gaming sector is also rising, with veterans making up

a larger portion of the workforce. The industry itself is maturing, with a growing number of experienced professionals contributing to its development. Additionally, the number of foreign employees in the Dutch gaming industry is increasing, both because certain positions require specific expertise and due to the difficulty in finding local talent for certain roles, such as those in marketing requiring knowledge of particular languages. Larger companies typically have diverse teams, and there is a noticeable rise in companies founded by expatriates (Dutch Game Garden, 2021).

While gaming remains the primary focus, it is closely intertwined with broader technological advancements, particularly in the context of diversity, equity, and inclusion initiatives across the tech industry. The Dutch tech sector, including the gaming industry, is experiencing a growing focus on diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) reflecting broader societal shifts toward inclusivity. According to the State of Inclusion in Dutch Tech report by Diverse Leaders in Tech (2023), 66% of tech employees believe addressing DEI is essential for their organizations. However, a significant perception gap remains, with 45% of non-Western employees reporting unequal treatment, and 1 in 3 expressing discomfort working with colleagues wearing a hijab. Despite these challenges, DEI is increasingly seen as a business enabler, with companies that prioritize diversity being 70% more likely to capture new markets and 87% more likely to make better decisions. This demonstrates the potential for the gaming industry to enhance both social equity and business outcomes by fostering more inclusive environments (Diverse Leaders in Tech, 2023).

6.4. Poland

As reported by the Polish Agency for Enterprise Development, Poland currently has the second largest European gaming industry, behind the UK and on a par with France, while boasting 23–37% growth year on year since 2017 (PARP, 2024). The industry includes 20 million gamers and generates \$944.9 million in revenue, according to the Polish Agency for Enterprise Development (Polish Agency for Enterprise Development, 2020). Nearly 8 million women, or 47% of all gamers in Poland, are actively involved in gaming, with 2.3 million playing daily, and 22% of female gamers describing gaming as their passion (Dziewczynowgrze, 2024).

Consumer protection

The legal framework for video games in Poland is influenced by both national and EU laws. The primary national legislation includes the Act on the Protection of Minors from Harmful Content (Ustawa o Ochronie Ma³oletnich przed Treściami Szkodliwymi), which establishes guidelines for content that may be harmful to minors, including violent or sexually explicit material. This law aligns with the EU's Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD), which seeks to protect minors from harmful content across all media platforms, including video games (European Commission, 2018).

Additionally, the Polish Penal Code contains provisions that address the illegal distribution of video games containing prohibited content, such as child pornography, extreme violence, or content inciting hatred (Kodeks Karny, 1997). Violations of these laws can result in significant fines and imprisonment, demonstrating Poland's commitment to regulating content within the industry.

Data protection and Age Ratings

As a member state of the EU, Poland must comply with broader European regulations that affect the video game industry. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) also applies to Poland and impacts how video game companies handle user data. Polish companies must ensure that their games comply with GDPR requirements, including obtaining consent for data collection and providing clear privacy policies (European Parliament, 2016). Non-compliance with GDPR can result in substantial fines, which can impact the financial viability of game developers.

Another important regulation is the Digital Content Directive (DCD), which sets out the rights of consumers when purchasing digital content, including video games. The directive ensures that consumers in Poland have the right to refunds or repairs for defective digital products, aligning the country's consumer protection laws with those of other EU member states (European Union, 2019).

Poland also utilises the PEGI system for age ratings and content classification. The system assigns age ratings of 3, 7, 12, 16, and 18, based on the content of the game, such as violence, language, and sexual content.

While the PEGI rating system is not legally binding, it is widely adhered to by Polish retailers and digital platforms. The Ministry of Culture and National Heritage of Poland promotes the use of PEGI ratings to ensure that parents and guardians can make informed decisions about the games their children play. Additionally, Polish law prohibits the sale of games rated PEGI 18 to minors, reflecting the government's commitment to protecting young audiences from potentially harmful content (Ustawa o Ochronie Ma³oletnich przed Treściami Szkodliwymi, 2010).

Poland has a history of limited censorship when it comes to video games, primarily focusing on the prohibition of content that violates legal standards. The government does not typically ban games for political or ideological reasons, allowing developers a relatively high degree of creative freedom. However, games that include content deemed illegal under Polish law, such as hate speech or the promotion of violence against specific groups, can be subject to bans or modifications before being allowed for sale (Kodeks Karny, 1997).

One notable example of content regulation occurred in 2019 when the Polish government reviewed the game *Mortal Kombat 11* due to its graphic violence. While the game was ultimately allowed for sale, it was classified as PEGI 18, and retailers were reminded to strictly enforce age verification measures (Gry Online, 2019).

Government Support for the Video Game Industry

The Polish government recognises the economic potential of the video game industry and has implemented a series of incentives to support its growth. One of the key initiatives is the GameINN program, launched in 2016 by the National Centre for Research and Development (NCBR). GameINN provides financial grants to video game companies for research and development projects, with the goal of fostering innovation and increasing the global competitiveness of Polish games (NCBR, 2016). Through this programme the government encourages projects that promote diverse perspectives in game development, whether through diverse character representation, culturally rich narratives, or inclusive game mechanics.

Additionally, the government offers tax incentives for companies in the creative industries, including video game developers. These incentives include deductions for research and development expenses, which can significantly reduce the financial burden on companies during the development phase of a game. In Poland, “programmers and developers who create copyrighted works, such as computer programs, applications, or games, can benefit from a tax advantage known as the “50% tax-deductible costs” or “50% TDC.” This provision allows authors to deduct 50% of their income from the transfer or use of copyrights as tax-deductible expenses” (Ntiative, 2024) .The success of these policies is evident in the rapid growth of the industry, with Poland now being home to over 400 game development studios (Polish Investment and Trade Agency, 2022).

Industry Challenges

One of the primary challenges is the ongoing issue of “crunch” culture, where developers are required to work long hours to meet project deadlines. This practice raises concerns about the well-being of employees and the sustainability of the industry (IGN, 2021). The government has yet to implement specific regulations addressing labour practices in the video game industry, which may become a focus in future policy discussions.

Furthermore, the rise of digital distribution platforms, such as Steam, Epic Games Store, and PlayStation Network introduces new challenges related to taxation and regulation. The international nature of digital sales where games are purchased across borders often bypasses traditional retail models. One key challenge is determining which tax rate applies to digital purchases. In the EU, the Value-Added Tax (VAT) is applied based on the consumer’s location, not where the company is based. This requires platforms to manage a complex system of taxes that vary by country.

The Polish government is working to adapt its tax policies to ensure that digital sales are appropriately taxed, but the rapidly evolving nature of the industry makes this a complex issue (Ministry of Finance, 2021).

Diversity

Diversity within the Polish video game industry has increasingly become a focus of both governmental policy and industry practice. Historically, the industry has been dominated by male developers, with limited representation of women and minority groups. However, in recent years, there has been a conscious effort to promote inclusivity and diversity, driven by both domestic initiatives and alignment with broader EU diversity policies.

One significant development is the establishment of diversity and inclusion (D&I) programmes within major game development companies, such as CD Projekt Red and Techland. These programs aim to create a more inclusive work environment by promoting gender equality, supporting LGBTQ+ employees, and encouraging the participation of underrepresented groups in the gaming industry (CD Projekt Red, n.d.). Perspektywy Education Foundation, a well-known non-profit organisation that helps young people in choosing their education and career path for almost 25 years, have now joined forces for a shared project” Girls in the Game! supporting the education of young women in the area of new technologies and preparing them for work in the video games industry. Besides these private initiatives, more than 50 universities across the country offer formal education for game development. The percentage of women in the industry is one of the highest in the world, at around 24% (GGI, 2024) In addition to the efforts from major game development companies, the Polish government’s alignment with broader EU diversity policies has played a subtle but impactful role in promoting inclusivity within the gaming industry. While the private sector has taken visible steps to implement diversity and inclusion (D&I) programmes, the government’s influence can be seen through its support of educational and funding initiatives that encourage diverse participation in the tech and creative sectors. For instance, Poland has benefited from the EU’s *Creative Europe* and *Erasmus+* programmes, which include provisions aimed at fostering cultural diversity and gender equality in creative industries, including gaming (European Commission, 2022). Furthermore, national educational policies in Poland have increasingly emphasized STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education, with targeted campaigns to encourage women and minorities to pursue careers in these fields. Initiatives like the “Women in Tech” conference, supported by governmental and academic institutions, aim to reduce the gender gap in tech and inspire young women to enter the industry (Women in Tech Poland, 2023). These educational initiatives are complemented by industry partnerships with

universities, where companies like CD Projekt Red collaborate on mentorship and scholarship programmes to provide opportunities for underrepresented groups. This synergy between private industry efforts and educational policy goals highlights a broader commitment to fostering a more diverse and inclusive gaming landscape in Poland.

6.5. The UK

Gaming is the largest home entertainment industry in the UK. The regulation of video games in the UK is comprehensive, aiming to protect consumers, particularly minors, from unsuitable content and ensuring fair trading practices. The combination of age ratings, legal restrictions, consumer rights, and advertising standards work together trying to create a safer gaming environment. The UK has an estimated 36.08 million gamers ahead of France 27.21 million (Statista, 2023). The UK Games Industry Census (2022) reveals that the industry's workforce is relatively young compared to the broader UK labour market. In terms of ethnic diversity, 89% of the workforce identifies as white. The industry is notably international, with nearly 30% of workers coming from outside the UK. There has been a slight rise in the representation of women and non-binary individuals since the 2020 census. The gender makeup of the industry has diversified slightly with men making up two thirds of workers. Additionally, 24% of the workforce identifies as LGBTQ+ (bisexual, lesbian, gay, or another sexuality), which is significantly higher than the percentage in the general UK population. Social background and education levels have remained stable, with most workers coming from professional households and holding undergraduate degrees. Physical and neurodevelopmental conditions, particularly ADHD and autism, are more common among games industry employees than in the general population.

Data protection & Age Ratings

The UK also uses the PEGI rating system that provides age ratings and content descriptors to inform consumers about the suitability of a game for different age groups. According to the Video Recordings Act (1984) and (2010) video games that are sold in the UK are required to carry an age rating and it makes it illegal to rent or sell a video game under the specific age rating. Retailers must take note of and comply with all legislation applicable to the sale, hire, exchange and loan of video works and games to avoid committing criminal offences.

In October 2023, the UK's long-anticipated Online Safety Act (OSA) became law, forming part of the complex web of new legislation promoting online safety across the globe including the EU's Digital Services Act, and Ireland's Online Safety and Media Regulation Act 2022.

The OSA is one of the world's most ambitious online safety laws, placing significant responsibilities on up to 100,000 services. Any platform with "user-to-user" functionality could fall under its scope, including games with online multiplayer text or video communication, content creation, metaverse features or virtual reality, and live streaming. With the UK media regulator Ofcom's strong emphasis on child protection and requirements for companies to enhance user age verification, gaming companies offering user-to-user services will likely face increased regulatory scrutiny and need to implement substantial changes to comply with the OSA's provisions, expected to take effect in 2025.

Provisions of the Digital Economy Act 2017 are aimed to protect children from inappropriate content online by implementing stricter age verification for online sales of adult-rated games. In addition, online platforms have to adhere to strict age verification mechanisms to prevent underage access to PEGI 18 games. The main goal of the Consumer Rights Act 2015 is to ensure that video games meet certain standards, including being of satisfactory quality and as described. Satisfactory quality means that the game should be free from defects, durable, safe, and perform as reasonably expected based on its description and price. Meanwhile, as described ensures that the game's features, mechanics, and capabilities align with what is advertised, such as including specific content or features promised in marketing materials.

In an interview with a Senior Research Analyst from the UK, there were significant gaps in the gaming industry identified, highlighting that current legislation fails to adequately address these issues. Drawing on their expertise regarding the UK's privacy laws, the interviewee noted that the UK has made progress in promoting privacy regulations in the gaming sector, specifically by encouraging protections for children's rights. However, they observed that other countries are slower to implement similar measures, creating a gap in consistent global standards for privacy and child protection in game development.

Consumer protection

Although the concept of children's rights is recognised, its application in business practices remains inadequate, and the existing measures are neither clear nor sufficient. One major concern of parents, lawmakers, and educators are in-game purchases and loot boxes. However, loot boxes are not classified as gambling in UK law even though the Gambling Commission monitors their use and potential impact on children.

Debates about regulating loot boxes more strictly are ongoing, with particular focus on improving protections for children and young people. The UK has recently issued new principles to address the issue of loot boxes in video games. These guidelines aim to restrict access for underage players by requiring parental consent, disclose the presence of loot boxes before purchasing or downloading a game, and provide transparent information on the probability of winning rewards. These measures are part of a broader effort to address concerns about the potential harm caused by loot boxes, but more comprehensive regulation is still lacking. While the UK government emphasises the need for increased safeguards, the guidance suggests a gradual approach, awaiting further developments in regulation (Fieldfisher, 2023; Game World Observer, 2023).

The government views are that purchases of loot boxes should be unavailable to all children, unless they are enabled by a parent or guardian (UK government (2022) UK Govt response to call for evidence on loot boxes in video games [Government response to the call for evidence on loot boxes in video games - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations/government-response-to-the-call-for-evidence-on-loot-boxes-in-video-games)). The UK government decided not to regulate loot boxes under existing gambling laws following an inquiry started in 2020 by the Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS). The UK Government has asked the stakeholders in the gaming industry to self-regulate loot box purchases (DCMS, 2022). Loot boxes, which are virtual items that players can buy with real money or in-game currency, have raised global concerns that mainly involve the potential for gambling-like behaviour, risk of addiction, lack of transparency leading to likelihood of excessive spending (Moshirnia, 2019), especially for games popular with children, “exposing children to same risks as traditional gambling” (Liu, 2019, p. 764). The items to purchase can range from cosmetic enhancements to game-changing rewards, the latter often criticised as “pay-to-win” (Zendle et al., 2019).

The DCMS likened loot boxes to collectible cards rather than gambling, noting they usually lack real-world value and mainly enhance gameplay through cosmetic items or minor gameplay benefits, rather than providing a direct competitive advantage. Additionally, the DCMS emphasised that while loot boxes can offer randomised rewards, their primary function is to offer players a sense of excitement and progression, similar to the thrill of collecting rare cards, without the financial risk associated with gambling.

In addition, all players, including children, should be supported with spending controls and clear, accessible information to promote safe and responsible gaming. However, it is important to acknowledge that while children may be aware of the costs associated with in-game purchases, they often lack the full comprehension of the value of money or the challenges involved in earning it in real life. This disconnect is particularly significant given that in-game purchases involve spending real money on virtual items that do not equate to tangible commodities, “the act of purchasing additional content itself should psychologically be as far away from spending money as possible” (Tomiaë, 2018, p.19). Better evidence and research, enabled by improved access to data, should be developed to inform future policy making on loot boxes and video games more broadly to assess the long-term impact on players’ behaviour, mental health, and financial habits, and to guide the development of effective, evidence-based regulations.

The DPA 2018 is the UK’s implementation of the GDPR and controls how personal information is used by organisations, businesses or the government (Data Protection Act, 2018). Under the DPA 2018, gaming companies operating in the UK are required to comply with strict guidelines on how they handle personal data. This includes ensuring transparency in data collection practices, obtaining explicit consent from players (especially when processing sensitive data such as location, personal preferences, and payment details), and offering players the right to access, modify, or request the deletion of their data. Additionally, the law imposes an obligation on gaming companies to implement robust security measures to prevent unauthorised access to or misuse of personal information.

Many games, particularly mobile and online multiplayer games, attract a large base of younger players. The DPA 2018, in line with GDPR provisions, enforces stricter rules around the processing of data for children under the age of 13 (Data Protection Act

2018, Section 9). Gaming companies must not only ensure they have proper consent from guardians for processing children's data, but they also need to design their systems to be age-appropriate, protecting minors from privacy risks and inappropriate content.

7. Outlook: Future Directions and Challenges in the Governance of the Gaming Industry

As the European video gaming industry continues to grow, these regulatory divergences present both challenges and opportunities. The increasing convergence of gaming with other digital services, such as social media and e-commerce, will likely drive further regulatory scrutiny, particularly concerning data protection and consumer rights. Moreover, the ongoing debate around loot boxes may push the EU towards more harmonised regulations, especially as concerns about gambling and youth protection intensify.

One of the main issues are investment challenges. A game developer that we interviewed in Germany, for example, stated that funding is provided at the state level, but each state operates differently, with varying requirements and criteria for what they will fund. This creates a fragmented system where game developers can experience completely different levels of support and funding options, even if they relocate within the same country. This inconsistency and lack of cohesion present further hurdles for game studios trying to navigate the industry's financial landscape. As a result, game development in Europe tends to rely heavily on grants and public funds, which, though available, are often challenging to secure. The quality of these funding opportunities at the European level is moderate, making it a difficult route for many studios.

Developers often struggle to secure funding between the pre-production phase and creating a demo or vertical slice³ necessary to attract publishers. Although some support exists, like the *Creative Europe* program, there is a lack of schemes that help bridge this critical funding gap.

New studios, particularly those without established backgrounds or resources, find it unsustainable to progress from concept to demo. Many developers either rely on previous student projects or have to work part-time to sustain themselves during early development stages, highlighting a practical barrier in the industry.

³ A vertical slice is a build or prototype that incorporates elements of all the various layers of a system (Gestwick & McNely, 2012, p.22).

Despite recent layoffs across the video game industry, there remains a significant imbalance in the labour market. Junior developers and fresh graduates struggle to find employment, while there is still a shortage of experienced senior talent, particularly in specialised fields such as backend engineering and free-to-play game design. This shortage of experienced talent represents a major challenge for the industry, limiting the growth potential of game studios.

Universities and vocational programs need to enhance the quality and relevance of their curricula to meet the evolving demands of the video game industry. Specialisation in fields like AI, server-side technologies, and monetization strategies should be encouraged to better prepare students for real-world challenges. Europe must strengthen its appeal to global talent by simplifying visa processes, offering competitive compensation packages, and promoting Europe as an exciting and innovative hub for game development. This could be achieved in part through EU-wide programmes or initiatives aimed at making Europe more competitive against other major gaming markets, such as the U.S. or East Asia.

The EU could prioritise removing bureaucratic obstacles that hinder seamless cross-border employment, particularly when it comes to remote work. This includes tax coordination, social security arrangements, and labour laws, making it easier for game developers and companies to collaborate across borders without facing administrative hurdles.

The critical importance of collaboration between game studios was emphasized by a Project Director and Funding Strategist from Germany. The necessity of such collaboration, involving shared intellectual property and revenue models, was highlighted. It was pointed out that collaborating on larger projects with higher potential for success is more advantageous than pursuing smaller-budget projects independently. Collaborative financial models were noted as particularly valuable, as insufficient cooperation between studios is considered one of the biggest weaknesses within the creative sector. Therefore, promoting collaboration among game studios is seen as essential for ensuring long-term sustainability in the industry.

Additionally, many developers, constrained by limited budgets, small teams, and scarce resources, attempt to handle all aspects of production independently. This includes attempting to manage specialized tasks, such as 3D animation, without outsourcing to external experts. Given the saturation of the gaming market, creating high-quality games and executing effective

marketing strategies have become more challenging. In this context, focusing on fewer, but more substantial projects and fostering collaboration is increasingly regarded as a more effective and sustainable approach.

Therefore, to enhance the sustainability and competitiveness of the gaming industry, it is recommended that policies be developed to incentivize collaboration between game studios. This could involve creating financial models that facilitate revenue and intellectual property sharing, as well as providing support for joint ventures that pool resources and expertise. Such initiatives would address the current fragmentation of the industry and promote the development of successful, high-quality projects capable of competing in a saturated market.

As a policy area, the role of human capital in migration policies is of great importance. Specifically, it is crucial to shape investments in a country's workforce in line with the needs of the labour market. This is especially critical for the growth of industries like the gaming sector. An interview conducted in the Netherlands reveals that one of the biggest challenges faced by European game industries is the competition among game studios and companies for skilled labour. This issue stems from the insufficient talent pool in regions where platform-driven industries are developing. The limited availability of skilled labour hinders sectoral growth and competition, posing a significant barrier, particularly for fast-growing sectors like the gaming industry. In this context, migrant experts and young talents play a crucial role. Migrant experts can be a critical resource for countries, but a more open and encouraging migration policy is needed to attract and integrate skilled professionals. At the same time, increasing access to education and career opportunities for young talents could be a significant solution to address the talent shortage in the industry. Investments in supporting the development of young individuals are critical for ensuring long-term, sustainable sectoral growth. Both the integration of migrant experts and the support for young talents emerge as fundamental components in the creation of policies to overcome talent shortages.

8. Recommendations

1. Funding Support for Early-Stage European Game Developers

Supporting early-stage European game developers requires targeted financial assistance, as many encounter funding difficulties when developing initial prototypes, such as demos or vertical slices, which are crucial for attracting publishers and investors. More accessible funding opportunities (through grants, subsidies, or low-interest loans) can help overcome these barriers, encouraging innovation and enabling developers to thrive. This targeted support is crucial for fostering growth and creativity within the European gaming industry.

The European Union has recognized the importance of a cohesive digital gaming market across its member states, aiming to harmonize regulations and create a unified market. This effort is particularly beneficial for sectors involving emerging technologies like artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and educational gaming. Funding programmes that prioritize research and development are vital to maintaining Europe's competitive edge in the global gaming arena, facilitating technological advancements and promoting a unified regulatory framework.

2. Towards a Unified Regulatory Framework for Loot Boxes in Europe

The fragmented regulatory approach toward loot boxes across Europe underscores the pressing need for a consistent, unified framework. Currently, the European gaming market is governed by a diverse set of national laws and EU directives, leading to inconsistencies in how loot boxes are regulated. This fragmented landscape complicates compliance for developers and creates challenges in enforcing standards that protect younger players. A unified European regulatory framework would not only address these disparities but also provide a stable foundation for monetization practices and youth protection.

Industry stakeholders have been advocating for clear guidelines, including age restrictions, player spending caps, and mandatory notifications on in-game expenditures, to promote responsible gaming. These measures aim to increase player awareness and ensure a safer gaming environment for all users. The video game industry, as outlined in the report by Video Games Europe and the European Games Developer Federation (2024), has taken significant steps to ensure transparency and player protection.

Enhanced collaboration between the gaming industry and policymakers is critical to achieving this unified approach. A cohesive regulatory structure could streamline compliance, making it easier for developers to navigate the legal landscape and focus on innovation in game design. By creating a consistent set of standards, Europe can both protect its players and stimulate industry growth, potentially setting a precedent for other regions worldwide. If evidence, such as interviews with industry stakeholders, supports this consensus, it could highlight a rare alignment within a traditionally diverse sector, emphasizing the urgency and feasibility of unified regulation.

3. Enhancing Inclusivity and Diversity in the European Gaming Industr

The gaming industry has significant potential to advance inclusivity and diversity, particularly for women and individuals from diverse ethnic backgrounds. To achieve this, industry-wide policy initiatives are crucial. These initiatives could include targeted training programmes focused on gender equality and cultural awareness, alongside the development of supportive work environments that nurture and amplify diverse voices. Such policy-driven efforts go beyond regulatory frameworks, emphasizing a cultural shift within the industry to create a gaming landscape that is more inclusive and reflective of its diverse audience. By prioritizing inclusivity and diversity as core values, the gaming sector can better serve its global user base, fostering a more representative and engaging gaming culture. Investing in these areas not only enhances social responsibility but also leads to innovative game design that resonates with a broader range of players, ultimately strengthening the industry's global competitiveness.

4. Digital Literacy, Youth Protection, and Engaging Younger Generations

To enhance digital literacy and safeguard young players, game interfaces should incorporate educational features that teach children about the risks of online interactions, such as the misuse of credit cards and the dangers of sharing sensitive information. Equally important is the role of parents and guardians in guiding and accompanying children's digital practices, fostering a responsible and secure online environment while encouraging informed and mindful behavior. At the same time, youth protection laws must be updated and strengthened through international cooperation to safeguard young users from harmful online content. Additionally, integrating youth perspectives into game development and incorporating media and game

education into school curricula can help foster responsible participation in digital spaces. By involving young people in game creation discussions, we can ensure that their voices shape both the content and the way it's consumed, promoting informed and responsible engagement with digital media.

5. Future Regulatory Trends in the European Gaming Industry

Future regulatory discussions at the European level, particularly those addressing loot boxes and in-app purchases, provide a unique opportunity to establish clearer and more consistent guidelines. While the EU has engaged with industry stakeholders in the past, there is room for more structured and transparent collaboration to ensure that upcoming policies reflect the industry's practical realities and consumer expectations. Enhanced cooperation between industry experts and EU policymakers is crucial for developing child-safe, thoughtfully designed regulations that stabilize the market and allow developers to innovate confidently. A more consistent dialogue between the gaming industry and regulatory bodies could help build a safer, more transparent gaming environment, aligning with both market needs and public interests.

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10. Appendix A

List of Interviewees

- Ruth Dorothea Eggel – Strategies Horizon, GameLab
- Thierry Baujard – French Tech Berlin, Expert in Financing and Investing in the Creative Industries
- Anne Fujie Heslinga – Gaming Researcher, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands
- KooPee Hiltunen – Neogames Finland Association, Director of Neogames
- Harald Koberg – Expert in Digitalisation and Gaming
- Manny Hachey – Founder, Accelerator Program Director
- Manfred Huber – Österreichischer Verband für Unterhaltungssoftware-ÖVUS
- Daniele Schmidt Fischer – UKIE, Senior Policy and Public Affairs Manager
- Emmanuel Martin – Ubisoft, Corporate Vice President
- Marjorie Volland – Ubisoft, Project Manager Corporate Affairs
- Colm Seeley – Insight and Innovation Manager, UK Interactive Entertainment (UKIE)
- Jari-Pekka Kaleva – European Games Developer Federation, Managing Director
- Pinelopi Troullinou – Trilateral Research, Senior Researcher, AI Ethicist
- René Otto – Deviant Legal, Lawyer and Founder
- Martine Spaans – Dutch Games Association, General Manager

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